

1 ***Thermal comfort and indoor air quality in low-income housing in Spain: the influence of***
2 ***airtightness and occupant behaviour.***

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10 **Abstract**

11 Thermal comfort and Indoor air quality (IAQ) in residential buildings with different degrees of
12 airtightness was studied in two climates in Spain. Behaviour was compared in the areas occupied
13 by day and by night. The IAQ of the buildings studied, erected before energy efficiency
14 regulations were in place (1939-79) and lacking mechanical ventilation, was compared to their
15 airtightness. The rationale for that approach was that under such circumstances air change
16 depends on uncontrolled natural ventilation (=opening windows) and consequently on the
17 outdoor temperature. Relative humidity was also taken into consideration, given the
18 condensation that may be induced where ventilation is insufficient. In winter in both climates,
19 the CO₂ levels were over 1200 ppm, with means on the order of 1900 ppm in Madrid and
20 1400 ppm in Seville and higher at night than during the day. Infiltration-mediated air
21 changes/hour appeared to be insufficient to maintain the house under healthy conditions and
22 the risk of surface condensation is higher in the most airtight dwellings.

23 **Keywords:** Thermal comfort; indoor air quality; residential buildings; airtightness; low-income
24 housing

25 **1. Introduction**

26 In today's buildings thermal comfort is directly related to indoor air quality (IAQ), which in turn
27 depends on envelope airtightness in buildings with no active ventilation systems. Those two
28 parameters are more closely related in lower standard construction such as found in social
29 housing in southern Europe, normally associated with lower income households. Unlike public
30 buildings or higher income homes, such flats often lack suitable HVAC systems that might
31 eliminate the dependence of IAQ on the envelope as a regulatory element.

32 Heat and water vapour, constantly exchanged across building envelopes due to infiltration (the
33 air flow through enclosures) have a direct impact on occupants' thermal comfort and indoor air
34 quality. Indoor temperature is a parameter widely studied in residential buildings, for its direct
35 effect both on occupant comfort and on building energy demand and consumption. The
36 implications of outdoor relative humidity have been suitably characterised and its direct impact
37 on electric power consumption in cities has been identified[1]. In contrast, the effect of indoor

38 relative humidity on domestic comfort and power consumption has been scantily
39 explored. Comparing simulated temperature and humidity to simulated temperature only, Moon
40 et al. [2] found that energy consumption was 4.4 % higher when the effect of humidity was
41 included. The inference is that when that effect is excluded, building energy demand and
42 consumption may be underestimated. In a similar vein, including indoor humidity as one of the
43 variables in HVAC control strategy would enhance domestic energy efficiency. The use of
44 enthalpy as an optimal indicator for achieving success on monitoring comfort for energy
45 refurbishment has been proposed in previous studies [3], but not yet analyzed on occupied
46 housing units under real conditions.

47 European authorities, Spain's among them, are planning substantial investment in the years to
48 come to rehabilitate and improve energy habitability in the present building stock, geared
49 primarily to meeting H2020 and subsequent objectives. Over 1.2 million multi-dwelling buildings
50 built prior to 1981 are expected to receive such support in Spain alone [4] [5]. The primary aim
51 is to raise the efficacy of the thermal insulation afforded by enclosures or to replace windows,
52 although no mention is made of airtightness or indoor air quality (IAQ). In southern European
53 countries with temperate climates such as Greece, Italy, Portugal and Spain, airtightness levels
54 are not limited by law [6]. Spanish legislation only regulates window air permeability [7], [8].

55 The most common retrofits for such buildings include installing new windows with better
56 thermal and acoustic insulation and airtightness and improving envelope sealings. Whilst such
57 measures generally enhance the indoor thermal environment and reduce the energy needed for
58 suitable control, they may also on occasion lower indoor air quality [9] and favour possible
59 condensation-mediated pathologies.

60 This article is an outcome of the research conducted for REFAVIV, and the beginning of the
61 research Habita-res, a new tool for evaluating vulnerable urban areas. Financed by the Spanish
62 Government's R&D+I Plan, the project aims to foster energy self-sufficiency and healthy
63 habitats. Its focus is the comprehensive rehabilitation of vulnerable quarters on the outskirts of
64 large cities built after the Civil War through 1979 (before thermal regulations were
65 introduced) [10]. The underlying conviction is that districts can be rehabilitated to near low
66 energy standards while improving the resident population's environment, health and social
67 situation.

68 This article analyses low-income multi-dwelling housing in Madrid, the capital city, and Seville,
69 chosen as representative of construction typologies in southern Spain. The aim is to identify
70 indoor parameter patterns in such housing, along with the relationship between envelope
71 airtightness and occupant behavior. Temperature, humidity and CO₂ readings are discussed and
72 compared in two different climates.

73 **Background**

74 In Spain as in the rest of Europe, housing construction was intense over the 40 years studied.
75 The residential buildings dating from that period account for 42 % of today's total census of
76 Spanish homes (source: Spanish National Statistics Institute) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Housing stock in Spain by year of construction.

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79 On the whole, those buildings' envelopes are characterised by fairly low energy performance.
 80 The façade and roof enclosures normally lack thermal insulation and a significant percentage of
 81 the façades consist in a single wythe of masonry with no air space. The windows generally have
 82 very simple joinery and non-insulating glazing, except where recently replaced [11] [12]. The
 83 flats in such buildings, close to half of the present stock, depend on natural ventilation (open
 84 windows) and the uncontrolled supply of outdoor air attributable to infiltration [13]–[15].
 85 Controlled ventilation systems only made their appearance in these buildings when the
 86 European EPBD directives were transposed to Spanish law in 2007 with the adoption of its
 87 technical building code (CTE), a circumstance with parallels in other southern European
 88 countries [16].

89 Given the type and period of construction, envelopes tend to be scantily airtight [14]. The
 90 generally accepted parameter for determining indoor air quality in such spaces is CO₂
 91 concentration[17], [18]. Carbon dioxide at concentrations higher in the indoor than in the
 92 outdoor air is not usually deemed to be a contaminant per se, but rather an indication of the
 93 presence of bioeffluents, a measure of occupant-induced contaminants and of the capacity of
 94 the indoor space to lower indoor concentrations via dilution and ventilation [19], [20]. Although
 95 as a rule the harmful effects of carbon dioxide on health are not associated with the
 96 concentrations normally found in buildings, concern has recently been voiced in that regard.
 97 Allen et al. [21] and Satish et al. [22] found CO₂ at concentrations routinely present in buildings
 98 to be directly related to cognitive processes. Agencies such as the National Collaborating Centre
 99 for Environmental Health in Canada, EPA in the USA and others are revising their
 100 recommendations on CO₂ levels in terms of exposure and the association with other indoor air
 101 contaminants. A need has likewise been felt for further study to acquire a fuller epidemiological
 102 overview. The general recommendation is to heighten official sensitivity to the effects of closed
 103 spaces on health, given the uncertainty surrounding the issue and the synergies between carbon
 104 dioxide and volatile organic compounds (VOCs).

105 Increasing building envelope airtightness in an attempt to lower heat loss and enhance energy
106 efficiency may reduce air circulation, which would explain the often higher CO₂ levels in modern
107 relative to older buildings. Since indoor air quality problems are usually solved by supplying
108 outdoor air, in buildings dependent upon natural ventilation greater airtightness should be
109 viewed as a higher risk of exposure to an unsuitable indoor atmosphere, particularly in light of
110 recent concerns that envisage a heavier impact on occupant health.

111 Such considerations have prompted a significant number of pilot experiences in which efficient
112 building construction has been geared not only to lowering consumption, but also to meeting
113 demands to enhance IAQ. Although generally undertaken in cold climates [9], [23]–[26], a few
114 studies in warm areas have also been published [27]–[29]. Such efforts tend to target new-
115 builds, however, where integrating such requirements from the drawing board stage may be
116 less complex. Fewer energy rehabilitation experiences have defined occupant health as one of
117 the primary considerations, particularly in warm climates [30], [31]. In most cases the main tool
118 for controlling the indoor atmosphere in residential buildings consists in mechanical ventilation
119 associated with heat recovery systems, such as required under the *Passivhaus* standard. Such a
120 solution is scantily plausible in many of the older and especially the lower income segments of
121 the building stock in warm European climates, however.

122 Raising envelope airtightness as a strategy to improve housing energy efficiency should be
123 attendant upon maintaining a certain air change capacity that would suffice, even in the absence
124 of voluntary user action, to guarantee the minimum required outdoor air supply.

125 **2. Method**

126 **2.1. Sample studied**

127 The sample of housing built in Madrid and Seville defined for this analysis, included flats highly
128 representative of social housing (the prevalent category) dating from the period studied
129 between 1939 and 1979. The procedure for identifying and classifying these units is described
130 in [32]. The buildings studied were selected after a lengthy process designed to suitably
131 represent the building stock. In the first phase, social housing developments were identified and
132 characterised within the city limits in the period studied. Subsequent analysis led to grouping
133 the developments into particularly representative types characterised by the features found in
134 each sub-period. A second grouping (covering 83 developments and 46,476 units or 47 % of the
135 population in Seville; and 73 developments and 57,478 units or 23 % of the population in
136 Madrid) established the essential morpho-constructional features of these developments,
137 identifying subject types by sub-period and building a matrix of typical characteristics also by
138 sub-period, all of which is described in [32] and [12]. Figure 3 shows the location of the
139 developments analysed in detail in Seville (46,476 dwellings) and Figure 2 the site of those in
140 Madrid (57,478 dwellings). Six buildings, three in Madrid and three in Seville, were tested for
141 airtightness and their environmental parameters were monitored for a full year.

142 The buildings chosen were premises with fully confined floor areas and volumes characterised
143 by low form factors, a characteristic feature attributable to the need to optimise construction
144 by minimising the economic and material resources deployed. These flats normally featured just
145 one small window in the main rooms and had bathrooms with no ventilation or that vented into

146 the kitchen. All the flats studied in Madrid were heated but none had mechanical ventilation.
147 None was air-conditioned, as is the case in most of the area's housing. Whilst the homes in
148 Seville were not heated, one had no air conditioning, another had individual room units and the
149 third dwelling-wide facilities. None had mechanical ventilation.

150 In Madrid:

- 151 - Case M1. The development chosen for the airtightness tests is located in Manoteras, a
152 city quarter on the northeast periphery of Madrid. Its 1204 flats were built in 1960.
153 Representative of linear typology, its enclosures consist in 1-ft brick. The users were a
154 middle-aged couple with one 16-year-old daughter. The flat exhibited normal upkeep,
155 but had not been rehabilitated beyond the replacement of the original timber for
156 aluminium joinery on its single glazed windows. Ventilated naturally by opening the
157 windows, the flat was fitted with an individual gas boiler for heating and DHW.
- 158 - Case M2. Here also, the development chosen for the airtightness tests is located in
159 Manoteras. Its 80 flats were built in 1973. Representative of a linear typology, it is
160 enclosed by a 0.5-ft brick+air space+partition wall system. The users were a young
161 couple with two children, aged 8 and 10. The flat had undergone major retrofitting: new
162 aluminium frame, double-glazed windows with thermal breaks, no thermal insulation
163 on the façade enclosure and sealing around the gas vent in the kitchen. It was fitted with
164 an individual gas boiler for heating and DHW.
- 165 - Case M3. The development chosen for the airtightness tests is located in
166 Hispanoamérica, a city quarter on the northern area of the city. Its 164 flats were built
167 in 1965. Representative of linear typology, it is enclosed by a 1-ft brick+air
168 space+partition wall system. The users were a middle-aged couple with one teenage
169 son. The flat's original openings had been replaced with new aluminium frame, double
170 glazed windows. The building was fitted with central heating.

171 In Seville:

- 172 - Case S1. The development chosen for the airtightness tests is located in Bami, a city
173 quarter. Its 554 flats were built in 1963. Representative of H-shaped apartment blocks,
174 it is enclosed with 1-ft brick walls. The users chosen were three young students. The flat
175 had been kept up routinely, but not rehabilitated. It had no HVAC.
- 176 - Case S2. The development chosen for the airtightness tests is located in San Pablo, a city
177 quarter. Its 270 flats were built in 1965. Representative of linear typology, it is enclosed
178 by a 0.5-ft brick+air space+partition wall system. The users were a childless couple. The
179 flat had undergone basic upkeep, but no rehabilitation. It was fitted with two split AC
180 units, one to cool the bedroom and the other to cool and heat the living room.
- 181 - Case S3. The development chosen for the airtightness tests is located in Diez
182 Mandamientos, a city quarter. Its 300 flats were built in 1964. Representative of H-
183 shaped apartment blocks, it is enclosed by a 0.5-ft brick+air space+partition wall system.
184 The users were a young couple with two school-age children. Basic upkeep had been
185 supplemented with replacement of the original openings with aluminium frame, double
186 glazed windows. Heating and cooling were supplied by a flat-wide system as well as
187 electric radiators (one per room), which were the users' option of choice for heating.

190 Figure 2. Developments located in Madrid and case studies (source: [12]).

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193 Figure 3. Developments located in Seville and case studies.

194 **2.2. Experimental design**

195 **2.2.1. Physical measurements**

196 An environmental data gathering campaign was designed to continuously monitor the flats
 197 chosen for analysis, which had been characterised previously for morphology, construction,
 198 floor area and composition. Two measuring stations were used, one in the main bedroom and
 199 other in the livingroom, to record air temperature, relative humidity and CO₂ concentration at
 200 10- min intervals for a full a year (August 2014 to July 2015). A Wöhler CDL 210 datalogger
 201 recorded the air temperature and relative humidity with an accuracy of 0.5 °C and 3 %,
 202 respectively, and measured CO₂ over a range of 0–9000 ppm, with an accuracy of 50 ppm ± 5 %.
 203 Outdoor humidity, temperature and wind velocity were furnished by Spain’s weather agency
 204 (AEMET).

205 As indoor CO₂ concentration, temperature and RH are never the same throughout a room [33],
 206 the sensor was positioned to detect a mean value, i.e., in the area where occupants would be
 207 breathing. That is, between 1 m and 1.5 meters high on the living room, and on the bedside
 208 table on bedrooms.

209 Indoor air quality can usually be assessed, often with CO₂ concentration as an IAQ indicator [34],
210 [35]. The standards in place establish air quality as low, medium or high depending on the
211 difference in indoor and outdoor CO₂ concentration. Studies have been conducted on the effect
212 of temperature and air quality (assessed as CO₂ concentration) on sleep in flats located in warm
213 humid climates in the absence and presence of mechanical ventilation. A similar study
214 undertaken in cold climates, specifically in Denmark, concluded that objectively measured sleep
215 quality and the perceived freshness of bedroom air improved significantly when the CO₂ level
216 was lower, as did next-day reported sleepiness and subjects' ability to concentrate and their
217 performance on a test of logical thinking [36].

218 **2.2.2. Airtightness**

219 Blower door testing was conducted to method A in Spanish and European standard UNE EN
220 13829:2002 and specific protocols [37] to determine the actual airtightness of the envelope. The
221 buildings were not tested as a whole. Rather each flat, conceived as a volume confined inside a
222 building with scanty any exchange with the adjacent premises, was tested individually. This
223 method has been shown to deliver the greatest amount of information with the lowest
224 percentage of error due to differences in the façade on a given building. The effect of infiltration
225 from adjacent premises could be ruled out, for in such typologies it normally accounts for under
226 5 % of the total [14].

227 **3. Results**

228 **3.1. Outdoor conditions**

229 Seville has a Mediterranean climate, with warm summers and temperate winters, whilst
230 Madrid's is more continental, with colder winters and somewhat cooler summers. More
231 generally, the warm season may be said to prevail in the former and the cold in the latter. Those
232 features must be borne in mind when characterising user behaviour and the facilities with which
233 the flats are fitted. The urban heat island effect identified in both cases was more intense in
234 Madrid [38] [39] than in Seville [40].

235 The mean monthly air temperature and relative humidity values in Seville and Madrid are given
236 in Figure 4.

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238 Figure 4. Mean monthly air temperature values in Seville and Madrid during the period
 239 measured.

240 Heating (HDD) and cooling (CDD) degree days (Figure 5) were used to assess seasonal thermal
 241 severity and determine possible overall climate-related demand for air conditioning. The cut-off
 242 values were 16 °C for HDD and 25 °C for CDD, to be the temperatures that best reflect the
 243 construction types and use patterns at issue.

244 Whilst Madrid's heating demand was nearly double Seville's, the differences in cooling demand
 245 were less significant and even greater in Madrid in certain months. In that period, in addition to
 246 vacation-related vacancies, flat use changes, with occupants spending more time outdoors and
 247 keeping windows open during most of the day. In the period studied, the flats in Madrid were
 248 exposed to much more accentuated wintertime demand, present in 8 months of the 12 studied,
 249 than Seville, where the needs were less intense and their duration shorter. The need for cooling
 250 was substantially lower than for heating in both cities and extended over fewer months, with a
 251 prevalence of warm weather in Seville.

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Figure 5. Heating (HDD) and cooling (CDD) degree days in Seville and Madrid

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3.2. Indoor conditions

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The mean values and standard deviations for each season and dwelling studied are given in Table 1. Daytime (living room) was defined to run from 8:00 to 23:00 and consequently night time from 23.00 to 8:00. All the bedrooms were occupied by two people except in case study S1, where it had a single occupant.

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In winter, the mean bedroom temperature in Madrid was 16.7 °C (ranging from 14 °C to 18.5 °C). Unlike the other two flats, M3 lay within the thermal comfort zone most of the time. In Seville, the mean bedroom temperature was 15.4 °C (ranging from 13 °C to 17.5 °C). The mean indoor temperatures were lower than in Madrid despite the more temperate values in Seville (4 °C to 5°C higher on average) due to the less intense use of heating. Similar values were recorded in the living rooms, although they were around 0.5 °C higher in Madrid as a result of daytime heating.

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In summer, the mean bedroom temperature in Madrid was 28.2 °C (ranging from 26.5 °C to 30 °C), whilst the living room temperature was around 0.5 °C higher. In Seville, the mean bedroom summertime temperature was 27.6 °C (ranging from 25.5 °C to 30.5 °C), whilst the living room temperature was likewise around 0.5 °C higher. In summer the mean indoor temperatures were slightly higher in Seville than in Madrid because the mean outdoor temperature was higher in the former city. The living room temperatures were only around 0.5 °C higher in both cities, despite their occupancy at the time of day when outdoor temperatures were highest and the absence of the passive natural ventilation found in some bedrooms overnight in the summer.

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In spring and autumn, indoor temperatures were closer to the thermal comfort zones: around 20 °C to 22 °C in Madrid and 22°C to 24°C in Seville.

278 In Madrid relative humidity values were widely scattered in winter, with a mean of 66 % in the
279 living room (ranging from 50 % to 80 %) and 70 % in the bedroom (55 % to 84 %). In Seville, mean
280 relative humidity was similar in the bedroom and living room and in all three flats, at around
281 65 % (varying from 55 % to 78 %). Those values were higher than the 40 % to 50 % defined as
282 comfortable by Spanish legislation and in some cases very near the 80 % RH that induces mould
283 in housing.

284 In Madrid M3 was fairly exceptional, for as the flat was heated all day, the mean relative
285 humidity dipped to around 37 %, much lower than in the other two cases where the
286 temperature tended to lie outside the comfort zone. That value likewise fell below the comfort
287 range, albeit only barely.

288 In summer, Madrid's slightly dryer climate was mirrored in a lower relative humidity throughout
289 the dwelling (mean 36 %, varying from 35 % to 56 %) than in Seville (mean 48 %, varying from
290 35 % to 75 %). Those values compared to the summertime comfort range of 45 % to 60 % laid
291 down in Spanish legislation.

292 In spring and autumn, the mean relative humidity recorded in the bedroom and living room was
293 very similar in the two cities, at around 55 % (ranging from 45 % to 73 %) in Madrid and 54 %
294 (43 % to 73 %) in Seville. In both cases the values lay within the comfort range 95 % of the time.

295 In all seasons and flats, the mean relative humidity was higher in the bedroom than in the living
296 room, which is consistent with the continued use of space where people are the primary source
297 of humidity.

298 Table 1. Case studies: temperature, relative humidity and CO₂ concentration by season and area.

		Living room (day)				Bedroom (night)			
		W	Sp	Su	A	W	Sp	Su	A
M1	Mean temperature (°C)	17.2	19.3	29.3	22.0	16.3	17.9	28.6	18.3
	StD (°C)	1.6	2.3	1.5	3.0	2.4	1.1	1.4	2.3
	Mean humidity (%)	56.9	50.2	33.0	54.6	61.9	57.0	35.8	67.4
	StD (%)	5.1	8.5	4.6	9.6	7.3	5.9	4.7	9.1
	Mean CO ₂ concentration (ppm)	1425	859	454	862	1461	1139	466	1137
	StD (ppm)	582	430	153	483	582	540	161	591
M2	Mean temperature (°C)	17.6	19.9	26.7	21.2	17.1	19.9	27.7	20.5
	StD (°C)	0.8	2.1	1.1	3.1	1.3	2.6	1.2	3.3
	Mean humidity (%)	75.9	60.1	38.3	61.0	77.9	58.4	36.6	63.2
	StD (%)	4.3	13.3	5.4	14.3	6.8	14.3	4.7	15.3
	Mean CO ₂ concentration (ppm)	2076	1157	439	1186	2848	1125	445	1602
	StD (ppm)	706	976	176	1113	1132	1130	212	1382
M3	Mean temperature (°C)	23.7	22.9	27	23.5	22.4	22.2	25.7	23.0
	StD (°C)	1.1	1.9	1.7	1.9	1.0	2.3	1.8	1.5
	Mean humidity (%)	36.8	38.4	33.7	39.4	40.3	42.0	29.0	41.0
	StD (%)	3.0	8.5	7.0	7.5	2.8	8.3	12.3	2.4
	Mean CO ₂ concentration (ppm)	1034	804	446		1031	848	487	
	StD (ppm)	291	376	93		290	381	90	
Overall mean, Madrid	Mean temperature (°C)	17.4	19.6	28.0	21.6	16.7	18.9	28.2	19.4
	Mean humidity (%)	66.4	55.2	35.7	57.8	69.9	57.7	36.2	65.3
	Mean CO ₂ concentration (ppm)	1750	1008	446	1024	2327	1132	455	1369
S1	Mean temperature (°C)	16.6	23.2	26.8	20.7	15.4	21.1	27.2	19.7
	StD (°C)	0.8	3.1	1.4	3.1	1.1	3.1	1.5	3.3
	Mean humidity (%)	64.9	53.6	49.8	67.0	59.3	58.4	50.8	64.7
	StD (%)	8.1	10.1	7.9	9.3	4.6	7.3	3.9	6.1
	Mean CO ₂ concentration (ppm)	721	538	483	586	452	445	438	460
	StD (ppm)	285	175	86	212	88	232	35	187
S2	Mean temperature (°C)	15.1	22.3	29.4	23.2	14.5	22.3	27.1	22.9
	StD (°C)	1.2	3.4	1.8	3.0	1.5	3.3	1.6	3.3
	Mean humidity (%)	65.4	53.1	44.5	59.9	72.3	55.8	50.1	62.3
	StD (%)	6.7	10.6	9.1	9.1	6.3	10.2	8.2	9.1
	Mean CO ₂ concentration (ppm)	733	521	444	523	1182.3	774.1	596	604
	StD (ppm)	503	298	77	324	1461	1325	576	848
S3	Mean temperature (°C)	17.0	25.5	27.8	25.5	16.4	24.2	28.5	24.7
	StD (°C)	1.2	1.8	1.9	1.0	1.1	4.0	2.0	1.7
	Mean humidity (%)	65.0	51.9	47.8	60.1	67.6	55.8	46.2	61.0
	StD (%)	6.1	7.4	6.8	4.2	5.5	11.5	7.3	7.6
	Mean CO ₂ concentration (ppm)	102	680	462	691	1059	753	465	690
	StD (ppm)	523	352	197	266	523	463	197	352
Overall mean, Seville	Mean temperature (°C)	16.2	23.7	28.0	23.1	15.4	22.5	27.6	22.4
	Mean humidity (%)	65.1	52.8	47.4	62.3	66.0	57.0	49.0	62.7
	Mean CO ₂ concentration (ppm)	825	580	463	600	1434	657	500	585

300 As mean CO₂ concentration differed between bedrooms and living rooms, they were analysed
 301 separately here, stressing the night-time area, continuously occupied for approximately 8 hours.
 302 The bedroom CO₂ concentrations given in Table 2 for each case study are graphed in Figures 6
 303 (winter) and Figure 8 (summer). In Madrid in winter the mean night-time CO₂ concentration was
 304 2327 ppm, ranging from 1300 ppm to 3000 ppm with peaks of around 4000 ppm. Here also M3
 305 stood out for its better infiltration-mediated ventilation. In Seville, bedroom CO₂ concentration
 306 averaged 1434 ppm, varying from 1000 ppm to 3000 ppm with peaks of around 5000 ppm. In all
 307 cases users routinely ventilated bedrooms early the next day, when CO₂ concentrations declined
 308 steeply in a very short time (Figure 6).

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310 Figure 6. Hourly fluctuation in CO₂ in bedrooms in winter for all the case studies

311 In winter CO₂ concentration was below 600 ppm 22 % of the time in all the case studies. Levels
 312 were lowest in case study S1. In all the others, they were in the unhealthy range from 20 % to
 313 40 % of the time (Figure 7).

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Figure 7. CO₂ concentration: percentage of hours below a given value in winter

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In Madrid in summer the mean night-time CO₂ concentration was 466 ppm, ranging from 370 ppm to 620 ppm with peaks of around 2000 ppm. In Seville in summer the mean night-time CO₂ concentration was 500 ppm, ranging from 375 ppm to 1000 ppm with peaks of around 2000 ppm.

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Figure 8. Hourly fluctuation in CO₂ in bedrooms in summer for all the case studies

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In summer CO₂ concentration was below 600 ppm 42 % to 93 % of the time, depending on the case study. Dwellings M2 and S2 exhibited higher CO₂ concentration than the other case studies and values of over 2000 ppm 11 % and 29 % of the time, respectively (Figure 9). Ventilation routines in S2 and the extreme airtightness value recorded for M2 explained those findings.

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328 Figure 9. Percentage of hours that CO₂ concentration is low a threshold in summer

329 **1.1. Occupant behaviour**

330 The hours of occupancy in bedrooms and living rooms and the number of occupants in each,
 331 along with reported ventilation times, are shown in Figure 10 for winter and Figure 11 for
 332 summer. The graphs also plot CO₂ concentration by time of day for a randomly chosen typical
 333 day in winter and summer to determine whether users' replies to the surveys were consistent
 334 with the occupancy data recorded.

335 The hours of occupancy and number of occupants reported varied widely. Bedrooms were
 336 used by two people at night in all except case study S1 (flat with students tenants), where the
 337 master bedroom had only one occupant. In all the case studies, intensity of occupancy and CO₂
 338 concentration were observed to be related in summer and winter.

339 In winter in Seville and Madrid both, dwellings were ventilated for 10 min to 30 min in the
 340 morning (Figure 10). In contrast, in summer windows remained open all night, except in S2,
 341 where ventilation was not continuous (Figure 11). CO₂ concentration was consequently very
 342 low in all six cases and depended on room use, which varied more in summer than in winter.

343 In M1 usage was consistent with the data recorded, with CO₂ levels rising in the living room
 344 during the day and the bedroom at night. Low concentration was related to high permeability.
 345 In contrast, the high airtightness in M2 was attendant upon likewise high CO₂ levels that could
 346 not be lowered with natural ventilation or infiltration. CO₂ concentration was lowest in M3, in
 347 line with the general data for winter (Table 1).

348 In S1 the number of occupants tended to be small, for the users were not usually present at
 349 the same time. This dwelling also had the lowest airtightness in Seville as well as the lowest
 350 CO₂ concentration. S2, the least permeable dwelling in the sample, exhibited the highest CO₂

351 concentration, while S3, with the largest number of occupants in the Seville subsample, had
 352 intermediate CO₂ values.

353 The bedroom-living room differences in temperature, relative humidity and CO₂ concentration
 354 rose when the doors separating them were closed. That may explain the differences in CO₂
 355 concentration between living and bedroom in M2, S2 and S3.

356

357 Figure 10. Hourly CO₂ concentration and number of occupants in bedrooms and living room
 358 on a typical winter day for all the case studies (L= living room, B= bedroom).
 359

360

361 Figure 11. Hourly CO₂ concentration and number of occupants in bedrooms and living room
 362 on a typical summer day for all the case studies (L= living room, B= bedroom).

363

364 **1.2. Calidad del aire**

365 According to a guide on efficient air change in housing published by the regional government of
 366 Madrid[41], CO₂ concentrations of 1000 ppm to 1200 ppm are indicative of sufficient indoor air
 367 quality to prevent adverse effects on health. Those values are also a good benchmark for other
 368 parameters, such as volatile organic compounds (VOCs), which evolve in parallel and affect
 369 odour perception. Low IAQ levels were observed in winter in Madrid and Seville and in autumn

370 in Madrid. In the other seasons optimal levels of indoor air quality were reached with natural
 371 ventilation alone (Figure 12).

372
 373 Figure 12. Balance between energy consumption for ventilation and indoor air quality (legend:
 374 S: Seville; M: Madrid; A: autumn; SU: summer; SP: spring; W: winter).

375 **Discussion**

376 Despite Madrid having colder winters than Seville (fig 4), higher indoor temperatures are
 377 registered (Table 1). Even though the low quality of construction of social housing on the period
 378 of the study has been reported in both cities, a higher amount of façades with air chambers are
 379 found in Madrid [12] than in Seville [11]. Also, better appliances for heating are used in Madrid.
 380 Eventhough social housing during the period 40-80 rarely included this service, the
 381 implementation of heating systems in Madrid has been increasing, particularly based on natural
 382 gas [42]. In Seville, electricity is the main source of energy for heating, which causes higher
 383 energy costs and the reduction of these services by the inhabitants of social housing, especially
 384 on vulnerable households. Poor thermal quality of residential buildings and inadequate facilities
 385 are more determinant in comfort than external temperatures, as described in some studies that
 386 point to the paradox that the areas of Europe with milder winters, where average winter
 387 temperatures are not lower than 5°C, exhibit greater variations of seasonal mortality caused by
 388 discomfort [43]. This distribution is repeated also in the case of Spain, where it can be concluded
 389 that there are higher levels of energy poverty in the southern than in the northern regions [44].

390 During the summer, higher outdoor temperatures are reported in Sevilla than in Madrid, but
 391 lower indoor temperatures are monitored in the former. This could reveal a more intensive use
 392 of cooling facilities in Seville.

393 Figure 13 and Table 2 show the airtightness values found with the blower door test, along with
 394 the CO₂ concentration, temperature and relative humidity readings by case study.

395 An indirect correlation was observed between n_{50} and CO_2 concentration: the higher the n_{50}
 396 values (the more permeable the envelope), the lower was indoor CO_2 concentration. In living
 397 rooms, the highest correlation was found in winter (0.56), when windows were kept closed for
 398 more hours, especially in the middle of the day when those spaces were occupied.

399 In bedrooms the indirect correlation was somewhat looser in winter and autumn. In contrast, in
 400 summer n_{50} and CO_2 concentration were directly related, for higher permeability prompted
 401 more leakage that contributed to ventilation and the inflow of air at lower temperatures.
 402 Occupants consequently felt less need to open windows than those living in flats with less
 403 permeable envelopes. As night time bedroom window opening routines were reported to be
 404 very variable in the spring, no correlation was observed.

405 The table listing the correlation between n_{50} and temperature shows that the living rooms in the
 406 flats where leakage was most intense had the highest indoor temperatures in summer.
 407 Nonetheless, in bedrooms, where the indirect correlation was much laxer, the most permeable
 408 flats had lower temperatures as a result of the beneficial effect of the ingress of outdoor air at
 409 lower temperatures than those prevailing inside.

410 The correlations observed between n_{50} and relative humidity also showed that the humidity
 411 generated by occupants was dissipated more effectively in flats with more permeable
 412 envelopes.

413

414 Figure 13. Airtightness (n_{50}), temperature, humidity and CO_2 concentration by case study.
 415 (legend: S: Seville; M: Madrid; A: autumn; SU: summer; SP: spring, W: winter, L: living room, B:
 416 bedroom).

417 Table 2. Correlation between n_{50} and temperature (T), relative humidity (H) and CO₂
 418 concentration by season and area.

		T	H	CO ₂
Living room	Winter	0.133	-0.606	-0.562
	Summer	0.728	-0.265	-0.235
Bedroom	Winter	0.116	-0.397	-0.454
	Summer	-0.290	-0.058	0.760

419

420 **2. Conclusions**

421 Mean winter CO₂ concentration in bedrooms was 1895 ppm in Madrid and 1434 ppm in Seville,
 422 with night-time peaks of 4000 ppm in the former and 5000 ppm in the latter.

423 In Seville, CO₂ concentrations in spring, summer and autumn were very similar to the outdoor
 424 values, given the practice of opening windows to lower the temperature to more comfortable
 425 levels during the hours with less solar radiation. In Madrid, indoor CO₂ concentration was similar
 426 to outdoor levels in the summer only, whilst lower values were related to the thermal comfort
 427 zone.

428 Measured in terms of carbon dioxide concentration, indoor air quality was found to be wanting,
 429 in light of the high values recorded, especially in cold seasons. Occupants were keenly aware of
 430 the need to open windows to ventilate their flats, especially early in the morning in light of the
 431 lack of mechanical ventilation systems. For that reason also, in winter, during the rest of the day
 432 flats were only ventilated by infiltration across the building envelope. The observed outcome
 433 was poor quality and often unhealthy indoor air, not only due to the high levels of carbon
 434 dioxide, but also to the risk of condensation.

435 Co-dependence was established between airtightness and a low air change rate associated with
 436 high indoor CO₂ concentrations, particularly in colder areas, although with wide scatter due to
 437 the variability in window opening routines and natural ventilation intervals. That relationship
 438 was much looser in warmer climates, where no clear dependence could be identified due to the
 439 significant differences in dwelling performance stemming from individual ventilation routines.
 440 Nonetheless, the amount of air inflows attributable to the uncontrollable infiltration stemming
 441 from poor quality enclosures, is insufficient to maintain the house under healthy conditions.

442 Occupants of dwellings dating from 1940 to 1980 were observed to ventilate by opening
 443 windows, often to the detriment of energy efficiency. In cooler areas such as Madrid the practice
 444 of replacing the original windows with more airtight elements was observed to induce
 445 condensation, such as in case study M2, found in the BD tests to be more airtight than any others
 446 in the sample.

447 Improving indoor air quality in Madrid and Seville would call for improved ventilation practice
 448 (except in the summer months) or the installation of mechanical air renewal systems. In Seville,
 449 more effective heating would be needed to raise winter indoor temperatures to meet comfort
 450 standards.

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